

THE QUESTION OF THE FORMATION OF SOME MEDICAL TERMS IN THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

N.B. Usmonova

Teacher of UzSWLU

Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

nadira.xadjimatova@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of some medical terms in Russian and Uzbek languages, as well as to the definition of structural and lexical features of eponyms in medicine

In the modern world, new concepts are born every day, new topics are growing in science, technology and art, which requires the emergence of new terms. Despite the large number of terms in Russian, they can still be distinguished from ordinary words. Terminology includes words or phrases related to professional areas of human activity, and names the concepts and topics specific to these areas. The purpose of our article is to study the origin of some medical terms. The terms are characterized by the distinctive features of the "external language", which can also be distinguished from the words of general use. This characteristic, of course, refers to a group of terms created specifically to refer to the concepts and facts of the sphere of professional activity. We are talking about word-formation tools that are primarily used in the formation of terms. It is very convenient to adapt word-formation tools for the formation of professional nouns and to specialize their meaning. This acquires a desirable phenomenon for terminology as a

regular association of means of expression with the content of concepts. The consistency of sign and meaning is especially clearly achieved by international methods, in which the meaning of prefixes and suffixes can be "deciphered" outside of their relationship to the base of the word. These include: micro, macro, front, post, against, re-; -graph, -gram, -drome, -mer, -meter, -plan, -cluster, -teka, -tron, -fon and below. (for example, microscope Greek micros "small", scopeo "look"). That is why, as a rule, they are so easily formed with the help of concepts and orders of formations that have similar meanings, reflecting the basis for the classification of terms, respectively. This can be traced most clearly in the terminology of modern medicine. Names of diseases with a fairly clear differentiation of its nature: inflammatory processes in the organs of the human body (appendicitis, bronchitis, bursitis, vasculitis, contact dermatitis, carditis, sinusitis, tonsillitis, sciatica, tracheitis); tumor formations (lipoma,

atheroma, hygroma, myoma, osteoma, angioma, there was food nearby, lymphangioma); body disease (neurosis, leukemia, multiple sclerosis, osteochondrosis, tuberculosis, spondylosis); severe pain associated with diseases (neuralgia, myalgia, arthralgia). Instruments for the study of organs (bronchoscope, gastroscope, rectoscope, colposcope, colonoscope, rhinoscope, laryngoscope, pharyngoscope). Research methods (bronchoscopy, gastroscopy, rectoscopy, colposcopy, colonoscopy, rhinoscopy, laryngoscopy, pharyngoscopy); fluorography, cardiography, vasography, cholecystography, cystography, renography, urography, salpingography). Medications (atropine, analgin, bifungin, reopyrin, nystatin, hemostimulin, pantocrine, cerebrolysin). Doctors are specialists in certain areas of medicine (cardiologist, endocrinologist, gastroenterologist, otolaryngologist, dermatologist, epidemiologist, urologist, nephrologist; psychiatrist, doctor, pediatrician). Medical sciences and areas of application (cardiology, endocrinology, gastroenterology, hematology, dermatology, neurology, urology); psychiatry, pediatrics, phthisiology). The principle of analogy for the formation of terms is generally very characteristic. This, in turn, creates prerequisites for standard structural and semantic models of word formation, in which parts of addition are repeated. Therefore, in medical terminology, frequency is the use of the therapeutic part: dirt-repellent treatment, water therapy, heat treatment, and so on. An important group are terms whose origin is associated with the names of those who made a scientific discovery - these are the terms eponym. The word "eponym" is a

word of Greek origin, literally meaning "the name of something". In medical terminology, where the influx of terms is particularly large, this phenomenon is observed: in some terms, the same surname Jaeger is used, but refers to three different scientists living at different times and in different countries: Jaeger's amputation is a procedure called the name of a German surgeon M. Eger (1795-1838); Jaeger's plate and Jaeger's keratoma are terms named after the Austrian ophthalmologist F. Jaeger (1784-1871), Jaeger's hook is a tool invented by the German ophthalmologist W. Jaeger (born in 1917). Such examples are not alone in medical terminology. The repeated use of the same surnames leads to errors and ambiguities, and therefore is undesirable in terminology. In the formation of eponymous medical terms, the suffix -ov (-ev) is considered to be very productive, which indicates that something belongs to the person who discovered this phenomenon: varoli bridge - varoli kypriqi, gunter's canal - gunter canal, etc. Of the 496 eponymous names terms in the dictionary "Eponyms in Anatomy" by S.D. Denisov and P.G. Pivchenko 152 eponyms (30.6%) have the suffix -ov (-ev), 272 eponyms (54.8%) have the form P.n. + I.p. Eponymous medical terms play a prominent role in naming new phenomena or discoveries in the field of medicine in connection with the established international tradition to name a particular discovery or invention by the name of the scientist who made this discovery or invention. Here you can select several names • * diseases (Pringle, Reynaud, Milkman, Marfan, Knott, Littlepringle - Reynaud, Milkman, Marfan, Knott, Little kasalligi va boshqalar); * syndromes

(Down's syndrome — Daun sindromi); anatomical units of the body (Horner's muscle — Gorner muskuli); * medical theories (Fletcherism); * Methods of research and treatment (methods of Ott, Pavlov, Pasteur, Golgi-Ott, Pavlov, Pasteur, Golgi metodlari); • drugs (vaccines Salk and Sabina - Salk and Sabina vaksinalari); * medical instruments (scissors Cooper - Kuper qaychisi); * Tests for the detection of diseases (Dick-Dick testi); * names of surgical operations (Bruns operation - Bruns operasiyasi); * names of genera of bacteria, consisting of the names of researchers (Klebsiella, Koch bacillus - Koh tayoqchasi). Some eponymous terms can form a whole word-building array. For example, using fragments of the compound words roentgen (on behalf of the German physicist Wilhelm Conrad Roentgen (1845-1923), it consists of and in one region of words with the meaning of "objects related to radiology": radiography, etc.) [5, p. 115]. The number of components of this word-building series is 30 word units. Clinical syndromes and symptoms associated with the names of literary heroes of century-old novels and stories of the 18th-20th centuries, as well as the names of historical figures, are interesting, creative and well remembered. Some of these characters are still popular today (Pickwick's syndrome is named after one of the characters in Ch. Dickens's novel The Pickwick Papers; Alice

in Wonderland Syndrome is the name of the heroine of the book of the same name by the English writer L. S. Carroll; Albatross Syndrome is the name of the character Samuel Taylor Koltros "The Legend of the Old Sailor"), caesarean section (the royal law of ancient Rome, allowing this operation). Construction terms-eponyms can be one-component, two-component and three-component, for example: Aaron's symptom (Aaron symptoms), Abdergalden-Fanconi syndrome (Abdergalden-Fanconi syndrome), Abdergalden-Kaufmann-Lignac syndrome (Abdergalden-Kauffman-Lignac syndrome). Compound nouns, along with proper nouns, also contain a common vocabulary that acts as the so-called reference words corresponding to generic concepts. Reference words for each branch of knowledge include a certain number of words. By area of distribution, they can be combined into three groups: some may have a special scientific character (syndrome, symptom, disease in medicine), others - scientific (in chemistry and physics - a constant, equation), others - general scientific (theory, method, law).). Therefore, an analysis of the origin of medical terminology shows that the specificity of the terminology dictionary is expressed in the fact that the term is a sign of a special concept associated with a certain field of knowledge. And the main thing is not that the word by origin has become this sign, but that it has become an independent language unit.

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